

Spectrophotometric Determination of Dissociation Constants of Violuric Acid and Stability Constant of its Cu(II) Complex

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Spectrophotometric studies of Cu(II)-violuric acid system indicate the presence of 1:2 complex in the pH range 4.0-6.5. The apparent equilibrium constant (K_1) has been determined by general absorbance-extinction-concentration scheme. The thermodynamic values of the first and second dissociation constants of the ligand have been determined while the third dissociation constant has been determined at $I=1.0$. The effects of pH stress and buffer compositions on the dissociations have also been investigated. The stability constant of the complex is found to be 14.60 at pH 5.5 and $I=0.10$.

THE coordinative interactions of substituted barbituric moieties are of great importance in elucidating various enzymatic and drug actions. Isonitroso barbituric acid or violuric acid forms chelates with different metal ions¹⁻⁴. Apart from this analytical potentiality, no systematic work has been done on this acid and as such it was decided to make a thorough study of its chelation to Cu(II). As a knowledge of dissociation constants of the acid is required, these have also been determined by spectrophotometric technique.

Experimental

Violuric acid (VA) of E. Merck chromatographic grade was used without further purification. Carbonate-free NaOH and HClO₄ (A. R., E. Merck) solutions were used for adjusting the pH to the desired value. Other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. All studies were made in conductivity water.

The pH was measured with an ELICO-pH meter (India) fitted with glass and saturated calomel electrodes. The uv absorption spectra of VA at various pH values were recorded on Carl-Zeiss Specord recording spectrophotometer. The visible spectra of the complex were measured with Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20. All absorbance measurements were taken with 1 cm cells at room temperature ($25 \pm 0.5^\circ$).

For studies of dissociation, a solution of 2.0×10^{-5} M violuric acid at an ionic strength of 0.10 was used; some measurements were taken at variable ionic strength ranging from 0.02 to 0.35. For determining pK_a , the ionic strength had to be maintained, of necessity, at 1.0. For studies on the Cu(II) complex, concentrations were varied at a fixed M/L (1:2) ratio and constant ionic strength (0.10).

Results and Discussions

The spectra of violuric acid (VA) in solution strongly depend on the pH of the media indicating successive deprotonation equilibria. The significant bands of VA are at 252 nm in strongly acid solution (pH 1.25) and at 220 nm and 312 nm in the alkaline medium (pH 8.0). Beyond pH 10.0, the absorption occurs at 325 nm with an isosbestic point at 318 nm. In a more basic medium (pH 13.50), the characteristic peak is at 310 nm. Interpreting the spectral behaviour in terms of three successive dissociation equilibria, the molecular acid H₃L would correspond to pH 2.50, the monoanion, H₂L⁻, would be present around a pH 8.0 and the dianion, HL²⁻, at about a pH of 12, respectively. To identify fully ionized VA i.e., L³⁻, the spectrum of VA in 2 M NaOH was recorded and a graphical estimation⁵ was also made. The extinction values obtained by the two methods agreed well.

The dissociation constants, K_c, have been calculated by the equations reported in the literature⁶. The K_{c1} and K_{c2} values were determined at several ionic strengths. The thermodynamic pK_1 and pK_2 values were determined by extrapolation method. The average values of the stepwise dissociation constants determined at several analytical wave lengths⁶ are K_{c1} = 5.88×10^{-5} ($I=0.10$), K_{c2} = 1.38×10^{-10} ($I=0.10$) and K_{c3} = 2.81×10^{-14} ($I=1.0$).

Determination of the stability constant of Cu(II)-VA complex: In presence of a large excess of Cu(II) ions, VA shows maximum absorbance at $\lambda=420$ nm in the pH range 4.2 to 6.5. For solutions above pH 7.0, the absorption maximum shifts towards shorter wavelength and an isosbestic point is observed at 412 nm. This indicates that only one complex is formed between pH 4.2 and 6.5 but formation of more than one complex may be

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involved at pH above 6.5. The 1 : 2 composition of the complex was determined by Job's method⁷.

The reaction scheme

is proposed to represent the interactions of Cu^{2+} ions added to a solution of VA in the pH range 4.5 to 6.5. At constant pH the apparent equilibrium constant K_1^{app} is then given by

$$K_1^{\text{app}} = \frac{[\text{Cu}(\text{HL})_2]}{\{M^{\circ} - [\text{Cu}(\text{HL})_2]\}\{L^{\circ} - [\text{Cu}(\text{HL})_2]\}^2} \quad \dots (2)$$

where M° and L° are analytical concentrations of metal ion and ligand, respectively.

The stability constant (concentration quotient) of 1 : 2 complex is defined as

$$K_1 = K_1^{\text{app}} \phi \quad \dots (3)$$

where $\phi = \left[1 + \frac{[\text{H}]}{K_{C_2}} + \frac{[\text{H}]^2}{K_{C_2}K_{C_1}} \right]$, and

K_{C_1} and K_{C_2} are the first and second concentration dissociation constants of VA. Knowing K_1^{app} and ϕ at a definite pH, the stability constant of the complex can be calculated from equation 3. As the Cu(II) ion and VA do not absorb in the region of $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 420 \text{ nm}$ of the complex, the extinction coefficient (ϵ) of the complex is found to be 0.28×10^4 at $\text{pH } 5.50 \pm 0.05$ and $I = 0.1 \text{ M}$. The apparent equilibrium constant, K_1^{app} , determined by general absorbance extinction concentration scheme and the stability constant, K_1 , calculated from equation 3 are $\log K_1^{\text{app}} = 7.15$ and $\log K_1 = 14.60$, respectively at $\text{pH } 5.50 \pm 0.05$ and $I = 0.1 \text{ M}$.

The effect of pH on the apparent equilibrium constant, K_1^{app} , of the complex has been studied. The K_1^{app} values were found to show no appreciable change in the pH range 4.2-6.5. A sudden lowering of the K_1^{app} values above pH 7.0 may be due to the hydrolysis of unreacted Cu(II) ions and/or formation of other species. A linear plot of $\log K_1^{\text{app}}$ versus pH with slope of 1.0 suggests that the dissociation of the second proton from VA, occurring in this pH range, accompanies the association of the dianion with Cu(II) ion. This is an evidence adduced in favour of the reaction scheme (1).

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